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THE ROLE OF SEMICONDUCTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES (THE CASE OF GESE)

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Annotation: Today, smartphones, tablets, computers, LED displays, solar panels, sensors, and medical diagnostic devices are made of semiconductor-based components. The article discusses the application areas and development perspectives of GeSe single crystal.

Key words: layered semiconductors, photoelectric sensitivity, band gap, hybrid energy-conversion, optoelectronic

One of the key pillars of the modern scientific and technological revolution is semiconducting materials. They play a crucial role in the development of information technology, energy systems, and optoelectronics. Today smartphones, tablets, computers, LED displays, solar panels, sensors and medical diagnostic devices rely on semiconductor-based components.

The main advantage of semiconductors lies in their ability to control electrical properties under different physical factors such as light, temperature and electric fields. This property enables modern devices to become smaller, more efficient and more powerful.

In particular, layered semiconductors such as GeSe (germanium monoselenide) have recently attracted great attention as promising materials for innovative technologies. Due to its excellent photoelectric sensitivity, thermoelectric performance and flexible structure, GeSe is considered a strong candidate for next-generation electronic and optoelectronic devices. (For instance a-chip, b-microprocessor)

a)

b)

Semiconductors are materials whose electrical conductivity lies between that of conductors and insulators. Their key feature is that conductivity can be modified by external factors such as temperature, light and electric fields.

The atomic structure of a semiconductor forms a crystalline lattice, where the allowed energy levels of electrons are arranged in energy bands:

- The valance band represents the energy levels where electrons are bound to atoms.

- The conduction band consist of energy levels where electrons can move freely and conduct electric current.

The energy gap between these two bands, called the band gap, determines how easily electrons can move from one to the other. In classical semiconductors such as silisium(Si) and germanium(Ge), this band gap is small enough to allow electrons to transition to the conduction band with relatively little energy input.

To control conductivity, semiconductors are doped withh specific impurities known as dopants/This process produces two main types:

- n-type semiconductors(where electrons dominate),
- p-type semiconductors(where holes dominate).

When these two regions meet, they form a p-n junction- the fundamental structure behind diodes, transistors, photodetectors and nearly all semiconductor devices.

In recent years, germanium monoselenide (GeSe) has attracted growing interest in both scientific and technological research due to its unique optican, electrical and thermoelectric properties. These characteristics make GeSe a promising material for a wide range of modern devices.

1. Photodetectors and sensors.

GeSe exhibits strong photoelectric sensitivity in both the visible and infrared ranges, making it suitable for light-detection devices. GeSe-based sensors can detect even minor variations in light intensity and are used in cameras, security systems and space telescopes.

2. Thermoelectric devices.

Because GeSe has a high thermoelectric coefficient and low thermal conductivity, it can efficiently convert temperature differences into electrical energy. This property makes it valuable for energy recovery and waste-heat harvesting technologies.

3. Solar cells and photovoltaic systems.

GeSe's ability to absorb light efficiently allows it to be used in thin-film solar cells, providing lightweight and flexible energy sources for next-generation technologies.

Photodetector

Solar panel

4. Nanostructured and flexible electronics.

Thanks to its layered crystal structure, GeSe is also promising for nanotechnology and flexible electronics. Devices based on this material can be used in bendable sensors and smart textiles for wearable energy systems.

The progress of semiconductors has always been at the core of humanity's scientific and technological evolution. Modern areas such as energy efficiency, miniaturization, artificial intelligence and sensor technology rely heavily on the advanced properties of semiconductor materials.

In this context, layered semiconductors like GeSe represent a new generation of innovation. Its thin-layered structure and multifunctional optoelectronic properties make GeSe suitable for use in both nanoscale devices and flexible, transparent electronic systems- paving the way for the future of smart, energy-efficient, and adaptive electronics.

Moreover, the combination of GeSe thermoelectric and photovoltaic properties can lead to the development of hybrid energy-conversion systems capable of generating and storing energy simultaneously. Such technologies hold great potential in smart home systems, renewable energy sources and portable electronics.

At present, leading research centers worldwide are exploring GeSe-based nanostructured detectors, energy harvesters and flexible display materials. In the near future, GeSe is expected to play an important role in composite structures and quantum technologies, further expanding the frontiers of innovation.

Thus, GeSe stands not only as a material of today but also as a cornerstone of tomorrow's innovative technologies.

Semiconductors are among the most essential components of the modern scientific and technological revolution. They have driven major transformations in computing, information transfer, energy generation and optoelectronics. In this context, the study of next-generation layered semiconductors such as GeSe plays a crucial role in shaping the future of innovative technologies.

The main advantage of GeSe lies in its multifunctional application potential. Its combination of photoelectric, thermoelectric and mechanical flexibility properties makes it suitable for a wide variety of devices. GeSe-based photodetectors, solar cells, sensor systems and energy-harvesting modules have already shown promising experimental results,

Furthermore, the compatibility of GeSe with nanotechnology and quantum-scale systems broadens its future applications even further. Ongoing research suggests that, in the coming years,

GeSe may serve as a key material for smart sensors, energy recovery systems and flexible optoelectronic devices on an industrial scale.

In summary, the role of semiconductors-particularly GeSe- in the development of innovative technologies is undeniable. They not only form the foundation of current electronic devices but also pave the way for the next generation of eco-efficient, energy-saving and intelligent technologies.

Through continuous research and technological progress, GeSe and similar materials are expected to become one of the driving forces of 21st-century scientific and technological advancement.

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